

Murtazoyeva Mohigul Sunnatillo qizi

Asia International University General technician Department of Sciences teacher
mohigulmurtazayeva21091993@gmail.com

ANNOTATION. This module is used to find out what the requirements are about teachers, the level of knowledge and character of teachers.

Key words : Module . Web page Create technologies . ASP technology . SQL language .

ASP technology .

ASP (Active Server Pages). It is a powerful technology developed by Microsoft for fast and easy development of WWW pages. ASP runs on Windows NT and IIS (Internet Information Server) platforms.

ASP is an internal technology that allows applications to be attached to Web pages. An advantage of ASP is its ability to use scripting languages (Visual Basic Script or Java Script) and external COM components.

VBScript has all the constructs (if, while, case, etc) for structured programming. In addition, this language has variables (it is not possible to indicate which type they belong to). Supports objects. Working with them is simple - Object.Property, Object.Method. There are also several additional objects (Request, Response, Session, Server, Connection, Recordset). In addition, the programmer himself can install the necessary components, for example, when working with e-mail "Download, buy...". [5]

Release command in ASP technology

The information to be shown to the user is sent to the output stream using the HTML language. The user's browser interprets this HTML stream. Response to facilitate information release. The facility is available. Output is performed using the Write method. For example:

Response.Write ("

##

In this way, the operation of writing to the internal buffer of the Response object is performed. After the script completes its work, the buffer is given to the client in its entirety. It should be mentioned that the client receives "top-clean" HTML, and the main thing is that ASP programs do not depend on the client's software at all. Other methods and properties of the Response object provide output control. For example, the Response.Buffer method controls whether the client receives the data using the Response object or whether it reads everything or not according to the end of the page . Response. The Redirect method redirects the client's browser to another page. When using this method, you should not use the Response.Write method on the page until then.

Input command in ASP technology

A program built in ASP cannot directly ask the user about anything. It can retrieve data from other pages or URLs. The input data is placed in the output stream and received using the Request object. To give the value of the var variable to the test.asp program, it is necessary to write the following sentence:

test.asp?var=abc

To get the value of the variable from the program, we need to write the following code:

var = Request("var")

If there is more than one variable, they are separated using the & symbol:

test.asp?var1=abc&var2=def

SQL language.

The database world is becoming increasingly unified. This process required the creation of a single standard language that could be used to create information systems that operate in different computer environments .

A standard language that allows users who know the command set to create, search, and transmit information, whether they are working on a personal computer network workstation or on a large HMI.

SQL (Structured Query Language, usually called « sequel »), meaning — Structured query language. It is a language that allows you to work on relational databases. The characteristic of these language expressions is that they are focused on the results, not on the procedures of data processing.

SQL itself determines where the data is located, what the indexes are, and even how the actions can be sequenced; these details do not need to be specified in database queries. The SQL language was developed in the process of creating MBBT DB2 at IBM and is widely used in large computer systems built on the basis of UNIX systems and on mainframes and supercomputers on machines with RISC processors. At the same time, it is encapsulated into internal programming languages such as PL/SQL and Transact-SQL, without being independent. In 1986, ANSI (American National Standards Institute) of the SQL language official standard work came out in 1992 this standard expanded . Whole language 30 ha near to operators have there are some versions little more , in some little is less . Har what MB each different to objects , that is tables , procedures , functions , representations , sequences and etc have

« Client -Server » to technology according to the user EHM (Client) . requests special Information on servers (Server) again processed , user exposure only request again work results will be returned . Of course , with a server communication to do for the only one language need and such language SQL is selected as .

That's why for everyone modern in relational MBBT versions (DB2, Oracle, Ingres, Informix, Sybase, Progress, Rdb) and even in non - relational MBBT versions (for example , Adabas) « Client - Server » technology and from the SQL language is used . in SQL information table in appearance to describe directed deeds concept a lot not (from 30 few) of expressions consists of compact language to create possibility gave Two type : Interactive and Embedded SQL is available . A lot cases both forms are the same different works , but two different is used . Interactive SQL Data of the base in itself activity shows and customer use for exit harvest in doing is used . of SQL this in the form of you command enter it immediately is done and immediately the result (if it exists if) you can see can Embedded SQL is another in the language created to the program from nested SQL commands consists of SQL interactive and placed in their uniforms a lot numerous groups or subvolumes there is . They are by ANSI attention received and conceptual level useful , but most SQL programs them separately again doesn't work , so for they are actually of SQL commands functional are categories .

- DDL (Data Describe Language) is a schema in ANSI describe language , objects (tables , indexes , views and etc.) creator from commands consists of

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- DSL (Data Change Language) is this in tables how values to be kept desired per minute determiner commands complex .

- DCL (Info Management Language) to the user known objects on known effect to transfer permission to give or not to give determiner from tools consists of SQL Standard by ANSI determined and now ISO (Standardization according to international organization) by acceptance done But commercial data bases programs ANSI SQL without warning expand , that is themselves considered useful each different properties they add

SQL query the language is Maium requirements based on givens to the base appeal from him request requirements answer giving the results get language Current at the time different givens base and their systems created But relational type all givens to the base appeal from them belongs to information get SQL language work developed In this language requests how tools using organize to be done stopping let's go That's it to say well , in some BBTS (for example , in Access) it without using to choose request or special example according to request letterhead as appeal by doing belongs to data is taken , such requests organize to do for while Base dannyx — Sozdat (Given base create) from the command is used . Request the result answer as table in the form of get can

SQL language now optional givens to the base request from him answer to receive provider model tool is considered This is the language with dating in real life own place full reflection seven will receive examples based on seeing we go out

Necessary concepts possibility as long as being viewed circumstances explain for is entered.

For example , in Table 1, the factory servants about information given .

Table 1. Factory

Name	Dob	Paul	Los	Department	Salary	Telno
Rustam V.	17/01/50	M	22	Admin	2700	1338234
Erkin J.	20/02/55	M	17	Worker	2300	1445754
Barot V.	02/07/75	M	21	Sales	2250	6506133
Paul F.	05/07/62	M	12	Worker	2250	420627 2
Edwin E.	12/19/69	M	4	Account	2000	1334567
Maria G.	11/20/72	F	4	Sales	2100	905994 4
Bianca A.	14/03/75	F	5	Service	1950	6789082
Dinara 1.	01/02/79	F	1	Service	1900	
Dolly S.	07/11/69	F	14	Account	2000	6789872
Clint E.	12/12/70	M	5	Tecknic	2400	5564672
Joan A.	04/25/62	F	11	Tecknic	2550	5515431
Star S.	30/06/67	F	10	Service	2470	
Paulina 1.	11/04/66	F	9	Worler	2250	1335675
Donovan A.	05/14/67	M	7	Worker	2250	1450986
Zilola I.	19/02/69	F	9	Tecknic	2400	9049301

This table consists of 7 columns and 15 rows. Each column has its own name.

Name - servants Name

Dob is the date of birth

Paul - sex , Los - in the factory the work seniority (period)

Department — in the factory servant working department

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Salary is the employee's monthly salary

Telno - phone number

The columns above are named matrix attributes. Each line contains information about a specific employee (employee).

one column has different lengths and types. In the Name column, the last names of the factory employees are used, that is, words with a maximum length of 15 characters. A dob column has a date type, a different length, etc. Column type and length are its attributes. As column 1 shows, these definitions are different and therefore should be defined accordingly when defining the table. Finally, in order to distinguish table 1 from other tables, it must have its own name. Here and henceforth, we name Table 1 << Factory >> .

When creating tables, they should not have 2 exactly the same lines. It should be noted that not all columns in the table define each row in the same way. For example, Paul, Los, Salary columns contain duplicate names. This means that they have a low functional weight, they are not suitable for uniquely identifying each string. Moreover, it is difficult to determine from them what this table is about.

In the table above, the Name and Telno columns uniquely identify each row.

A column or group of columns that can uniquely identify each row is called a key. They must be separated when compiling Table 1 .

Now let's learn how to create tables. When creating a table, it is necessary to give the name of the table, the name of the columns, the type and length of its attributes. SQL allows input of variable types such as string, numeric, realtime, date, etc.

A string type consists of characters and numbers used to describe variables. The first character must be a letter. Char — intended to represent a string variable of length no longer than 254 bytes.

The keyword NUMBER is used to describe numeric variables.

1.0E -100 to 1.0E+ 100 has been to 22 numbers in a circle have be will receive numbers describes . Date and the time Date standard in description is used .

He: - time determines (hours , minutes , seconds standard . For example , 18.02.2007);

— the date to express for Europe from the standard or America from the standard is used .

Now create Table 1 for the following our writing can :

```
CREATE TABLE factory
(id NUMBER(5,0) PRIMARY KEY,
Name CHAR( 15) NOT NULL,
Los NUMBER( 2,0),
Dept CHAR( 15),
Salary NUMBER (7 ,2 ),
Telno CHAR( 7)).
```

We column Name each one attribute to 15 characters have has been stringed variable length with we determined . In practice attribute length from behind according to more is given That's it thing with It depends that we are in advance stringed of the variable which meanings to the table to be included we don't know That's why for known one reserve that it was ok From this except empty seats reserve columns between of distance to growth possibility will give . Table 1 is also more attractive in terms of design when printed. The NAME column contains NOTNULL. This means that it cannot contain empty strings. Each SQL statement must end with a << semicolon >>

. For the given statement, EHM creates a factory table, but the table is empty because no data has been entered into it.

In standard SQL, data insertion is performed based on the INSERT command. This command allows you to insert a single line, the next line being inserted is generated by the return of the INSERT command:

```
INSERT INTO factory (Name, Dob, Paul, Los, Dept , Salary, Telno ) Values (Paul F. 05.07.1962, 'm' ,12 'worker', 2250.75, '420027');
```

All stringed variables to apostrophes the introduction it is necessary If we are someone of the variable the meaning if we don't know , in input his the meaning down to leave can , EHM his place automatic respectively space with fills

Example : INSERT INTO factory (Name, Job , Pol, Dept, Salary)

Values ('Clint E', 12. 12.1970, 'm\ 'technic' ,2400);

Such in case Telno and Los seats , until they are in order until it is determined , using EHM probel and zeros with is filled in process correct until close continue will be delivered . Separately values down the rest if , them also with NUII to fill can

Select command - b u in the department of the user tables with work methods seeing will be released . Select command of the SQL language main from orders one is considered This is a command all actions data row with provides . Below is the select command main opportunities seeing we go out

a) *View all information.*

Select* from tactory ;

(F) symbol of the factory table all columns choose need means

This result from the Select command after all columns name to give with if possible will be :

```
Select Name, Dob , Pol, Los, Dept , Salary, Telno  
from factory;
```

As a result All of Table 1 on the screen columns appear will be

Columns order in the Select command as specified will be :

b) *columns selective call .*

Columns separately to call in the Select command for show need :

```
Select Name, Dept from factory;
```

As a result, we get a table with Name and Dept:

d) *Strings choose to see* Information with when working most of the time from the table only sure one string to see must has been cases meeting stands Such without the Select command common appearance as follows will be :

Select - columns name ;

from — tables name ;

where is a string choose condition .

Example : All from Table 1 employees , workers choose for the following input need :

```
Select name, dept
```

```
from factory
```

Where Dept — dmik ; command to give it is necessary

As a result, the following will appear on the screen:

e) *Application of comparative opera strings.*

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<< equality >> sign was used to describe the string selection condition .

<< Equality >> sign, there are 7 more basic comparison operators that can be used to select a comparison condition.

These are:

!= — is equal it's not ;

> — big ;

Name

Rustam V.

Joan A.

admin

admin ;

Dept

< > is equal it's not ;

!> — given big it's not ;

< — from given small

!< — from given small it's not ;

>= is big or equal

<= is small or equal to

The following example to compare of operators application opportunities shows .

Example 1: From the Factory table the work 10 years of experience more than has been of workers their names choose

Select Name, Los

from factory

where Los > 10;

The result is on the screen

NAME Los

Rustam V. 22

Barot V. 21

Azamat T. 17

Dolly S. 14

Paul F. 12

Joan A. 11 comes out .

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